

Press Release
8 May 2024

FOODITY launches its second open call to fund data-driven solutions for food and nutrition

- The EU-funded project FOODITY will fund six data-driven solutions to reshape food systems while championing data sovereignty. These innovations will enable citizens to contribute to healthier, more sustainable food systems.
- FOODITY's €1M pilot development programme beneficiaries will receive up to €187,500, tailored expert mentoring, and technical support to advance their products and services over 12 months.
- Organisations wishing to participate in the FOODITY programme can apply to this open call from 8 May to 10 July 2024 to get the support they need to scale their solutions.

FOODITY (FOod and nutritiOn Data-driven innovation respectful of citizen's Data SoverelgnTY) is pleased to announce the launch of its Open Call #2 as part of a wider mission to develop a **dynamic ecosystem of digital solutions for food and nutrition that respect citizens' rights to personal data sovereignty** in Europe.

This EU-funded initiative has designed a programme for SMEs/start-ups, social innovation actors, researchers, and training organisations developing solutions for data-driven innovation in food systems and preparing to enter the market.

With six teams already supported in its first programme¹, **FOODITY is now launching a second edition to continue providing new opportunities to European food innovators.** The selected proposals will allow citizens complete control over their personal data, empowering them to make better — more environmentally friendly and healthier — dietary choices, thus contributing to more sustainable food systems.

The programme aims to address food systems challenges by leveraging disruptive, digital solutions to achieve the key priorities of the EU's research and innovation policy, **Food 2030**².

¹ [Meet the Innovators From FOODITY Open Call 1](#)

² [Food 2030: Research and innovation policy to make our food systems ready for the future](#)

These include food systems supporting a healthy planet, promoting nutrition for sustainable and healthy diets, encouraging circularity and resource efficiency, and fostering innovation and empowering communities.

The open call will accept submissions to develop solutions focusing on one of the themes — shopping experiences, education or services — or an open challenge.

What's in it for applicants?

The FOODITY value-added services

The FOODITY open call beneficiaries will access a wide range of added-value services, from **financial support** (up to **€187.500** per beneficiary) to **expert mentoring and training, group coaching, and technical support** to use the programme's GDPR-compliant data management infrastructure and food data components.

Pilots will be assisted in using the programme's **data architecture** and delve into **data management ethics**, among other technical topics. Training will also cover **citizen engagement** methods, given that engagement is a core activity throughout the programme to ensure solutions that meet user needs. Mentoring support will be focused on **business** topics, from innovation strategy to product development.

Who are we looking for?

The FOODITY innovators

FOODITY is looking for organisations with **technical, social innovation, and citizen engagement** expertise.

- Small or Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) and startups
- Social Innovation Actors (SIAs)
- Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs) and universities
- Training organisations

“The FOODITY second open call is a great opportunity for multi-disciplinary consortia to join forces and contribute towards a change in the food and nutrition domains. Also, to empower citizens' rights to data sovereignty through their projects”, says Samuel Almeida, FOODITY's Project Coordinator.

The FOODITY Open Call #2 is open from 8 May to 10 July 2024 (17.00 CET).

Do not miss out on this opportunity to join FOODITY in driving positive change in food and nutrition systems!

For more information about the open call, visit the [FOODITY website](#) and sign up for the project's upcoming [info webinar on 16 May](#) and [matchmaking event on 23 May](#) 2024.

About FOODITY

In total, FOODITY will invest €2M in its pilot development programme to fund 12 solutions demonstrating the potential of data-driven innovation in food and nutrition while boosting citizen data sovereignty.

FOODITY is an ambitious impact-driven project funded by the European Commission as part of the Horizon Europe programme. Over three years (2023 – 2026), the FOODITY team, comprised of seven partners from seven countries, will work to revolutionise European food and nutrition systems.

From top-level experts in ICT-based solutions for the food and nutrition sector (CERTH), technologies for user's control of personal data (JIBE) and integration of data commons into federated infrastructure (SOFTEAM) to experienced professionals in engaging citizens (F6S, AUSTRALO and SPLORO) and social innovation (ZSI):

Learn more about **FOODITY** and contact us at opencalls@foodity.eu for more information about our open calls.

For marketing and press purposes, please get in touch with raquel@australo.org and andrea@australo.org.

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